

THE LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF QODIR BAKHSHI'S "NORGULOY"
("KELINOY") EPIC

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article discusses the work of Qodir Bakhshi, a prominent representative of the Qashqadarya bakhshi school. In particular, the artistic qualities and unique linguistic features of the epic "*Norguloy*" – "*Kelinoy*", which holds a special place in Qodir Bakhshi's repertoire, are analyzed. Qodir Bakhshi's achievement lies in his deep understanding of the customs and dialect of the people among whom he lived, as well as his ability to weave profound meanings into the narrative. The epic "*Kelinoy*" ("*Norguloy*"), performed by him, occupies a worthy place in Uzbek oral folklore due to its unparalleled artistic richness and distinctive linguistic features.

Keywords: Bakhshi school, oral epic, *terma* (folk songs), *dombira* (traditional lute), repertoire.

In folk oral tradition, epics hold a special place. The word *doston* (epic) is derived from Persian, meaning "tale," "story," or "history." In an epic, a specific event is narrated using lyrical-epic descriptive techniques, covering a broad spectrum of life and reality, with one or two main protagonists and numerous characters. The plot is intricate and colorful. In folk oral tradition, epics exist in both poetic and prose forms, while in written literature, they are composed in verse.

In Uzbek literature, epics are divided into two types based on their creation. The first type consists of epics written in verse, with each stanza composed in *masnavi* (couplet) form, created by representatives of written literature. Examples include Yusuf Khos Hajib's "*Kutadgu Bilig*", Abdulrahman Jami's "*Haft Awrang*", and the epics in Alisher Navoi's "*Khamisa*". Epics in written literature are composed in *aruz* meter and are products of individual creativity.

The second type of epic belongs to folk oral tradition and is a product of folklore traditions. According to scholar M. Saidov, oral epics consist of poetic and prose passages, forming an artistic source—the text. Secondly, an epic must have musical accompaniment (though not every epic requires a separate large-scale musical composition). Thirdly, since the epic is performed by a single person, the performer must be skilled in playing the *dombira* (lute) or *kobyz* (bowed instrument). Fourthly, the *bakhshi* (epic singer) must have a good voice and master the art of singing.

Researchers consider epics a *syncretic* genre. The term *syncretic* (from Greek *synkretikos*) means "united" or "not divided into parts." In the context of epics, it refers to the harmonious combination of word, music, vocal performance, storytelling, oratory, and acting. Over centuries, epic singers (*bakhshis*) have mastered these arts, displaying improvisational skill in their performances.

Qodir Bakhshi (1937–1986) stood out not only for his rich repertoire but also for his pleasant, resonant voice and exceptional skill in playing musical instruments. Besides the *dombira*, he masterfully performed on the *dutar*, *rubab*, *tor*, *ghijak*, and *kobyz*, either singing epics or *terma* (folk songs), or adapting melodies from other instruments to the *dombira*.

The word *doston* also carries another meaning—"to be spoken, sung, or passed down among the people." Thus, the characters in epics are not only artistic images but also figures who enter popular discourse, earning fame and affection. As a result, especially positive characters become widely known and beloved.

Epics with thousand-year histories, such as "*Alpomish*", the "*Gorogli*" cycle ("*Gorogli's Birth*", "*Malika Ayyor*", "*Ravshan*"), "*Kuntugmish*", "*Rustamxon*", and "*Oshiq Garib va Shohsanam*", have firmly entrenched themselves in the hearts of our people. Qodir Bakhshi's repertoire included around 70 epics, such as "*Alpomish*", "*Yodgor*", "*Kuntugmish*", "*Shirin va Shakar*", "*Rustam*", "*Murodxon*", "*Yusuf va Ahmad*", "*Yusuf va Zulayho*", "*Gorogli's Birth*", "*Zaydinoy*", "*Gorogli va Yunus Pari*", and "*Shahidnoma*", along with numerous *terma* and folk tales. However, only a small portion of his known epics and a few *terma* have been recorded.

Qodir Bakhshi's (pen name; real name Abdi Rahimov) "*Kelinoy*" ("*Norguloy*") epic, in the words of literary scholar Abduolim Ergashev, exists in various forms—sometimes as *terma*, sometimes as a historical song, and sometimes as a full epic—and has entered every household in Dehqonobod, touching the hearts of young and old, men and women alike. Folklorist Abdumomin Qahhorov collected over a hundred different versions—epic narratives, lyrical songs, and epic variants—conducted a scholarly analysis, and defended his candidate's dissertation in 1972 on "*The Unique Features and Ideological Foundations of the 'Kelinoy' Epic Cycle*."

The scholar noted that among more than twenty variants, Qodir Bakhshi's "*Kelinoy*" – "*Norguloy*" stands out for its engaging plot, cohesive composition, and high artistic quality. According to Abduolim Ergashev, there are several reasons for this. First, no one had studied epics from the Samarkand-Qashqadarya-Surkhandarya and other *bakhshi* schools as extensively as Qodir Bakhshi, refining his skill. Second, he was deeply familiar with the *terma* and songs about "*Kelinoy*" sung by local *oqins* (folk poets). Additionally, Qodir Bakhshi drew inspiration

from the life story of his aunt, Norguloy, to whom he often said in his youth, "Aunt, I will make you into an epic." Norguloy, well-versed in oral folklore, would recount her life experiences to her nephew, dressing them in artistic form. All these factors contributed to the creation of Qodir Bakhshi's version of "Kelinoy."

*Ey ko'ringan, qorli tog'lar,
Bundan so'ltoq o'tdi denglar.
Ko'kda uchgan satta zog'lar,
Qonlar yutib ketdi, denglar.
Tandan jonni sotdi denglar,
Ko'kda oyi botdi denglar.
Boshin cho'zib tiklab turgan,
Go'sht qarashib g'ajir qushlar,
Bundan So'ltoq o'tdi denglar,
Qonlar yutib ketdi denglar.*

Most importantly, Qodir Baxshi concludes the epic with verses unlike those found in other baxshis' renditions.

*Oq o'tovning ustida,
O'n oltita oyquchoq.
Qarisa ham Norguloy
El og'zida kelinchak.*

According to Abduolim Ergashev, Qodir Baxshi transformed the daily lifestyle into an epic space and epic time in "Kelinoy", elevating ordinary individuals around us to the status of epic heroes. Initially, Qodir Baxshi recorded the "Kelinoy" epic under the title "Masharoy", while the second and third versions were titled "Norguloy". All three variants stand out from one another in their profound meaning and artistic maturity.

In the fourth recorded version, Qodir Baxshi incorporates traditional depictions of rituals such as setting up a yurt (*o'tov tikish*), performing wedding songs (*yoramazon aytish*), and bride's greetings (*kelinsalom*). These elements hold significant artistic and ethnographic value in preserving and transmitting the nuances of our people's customs to future generations.

Thus, Qodir Baxshi's rendition of "Kelinoy" ("Norguloy") is unparalleled not only for its unique portrayal of youthful love in various emotional states and its expression of virtues, modesty, and resilience specific to Uzbek girls, but also for its meticulous embodiment of national traditions, customs, and distinctive linguistic features.

In short, Qodir Baxshi's brilliance lies in his deep understanding of the customs and dialect of the people among whom he lived, his grasp of the noble purpose embedded in language, and his ability to artfully weave these elements into the narrative. The "*Kelinoy*" ("*Norguloy*") epic he performed holds a distinguished place in Uzbek oral folklore due to its incomparable artistic richness and unique linguistic characteristics.

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